

Incentives in decentralised autonomous organisations

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of competitive incentives on member effort and organisational success, providing insights for practitioners aiming to optimise the performance of DAOs (Decentralised Autonomous Organisations). By leveraging the power of economic incentives through token rewards, DAOs, a novel form of member-owned organisational structure built on blockchain technology, are able to foster engagement and contributions from their members. Since tokens represent a DAO's value, in contrast to equity investors, token financing motivates members to apply effort, enabling a DAO to incentivise higher efforts than other member-owned organisations such as cooperatives. This study aims to investigate whether the association between efforts and tokens can effectively motivate members to generate value for DAOs. Our findings seek to assist practitioners in decision-making when selecting the optimal organisational structure based on the number of members and the share of tokens allocated to community rewards.

1. Introduction

A decentralised autonomous organisation (DAO) is a novel form of organisation that has gained significant attention in the context of global advancements in blockchain technology and cryptocurrency. The rise of platforms such as “Ethereum” and “Bitcoin” has served as a catalyst for the development and improvement of DAOs. The initial motivation behind the creation of DAOs was to operate without the need for managers or hierarchical structures; instead of relying on automated tasks, a DAO functions independently without the involvement of third parties (Wang et al., 2019).

According to DeepDAO (<https://deepdao.io>), one of the most prominent and widely used platforms for DAO analytics, there has been a significant increase in the value of DAO treasuries, rising from \$400 million to \$22.6 billion by August 2024. Concurrently, global participation in DAO voting and proposal-making experienced substantial growth, with a surge from 13,000 to 10.9 million participants. The total number of DAO governance token holders reached 10.8 million, of which 3.2 million were actively engaged as voters and proposal makers. Illustrative cases of large DAOs include ResearchHub, a DAO dedicated to accelerating the pace of scientific research with over 5800 members, and UC Crypto Soc, a smaller DAO comprising a collection of like-minded University of Canterbury students passionate about crypto and decentralisation, with just 19 members. This contrast raises an intriguing question: Given their differing scales and operational contexts, is the DAO model truly optimal for both types of organisations?

Addressing this question could reveal whether the DAO framework is universally applicable or if its effectiveness varies significantly depending on the size and nature of the organisation, particularly when new organisations are formed.

According to DeepDAO's research findings, the total number of existing DAOs had surpassed 20,000 by August 2024, more than four times the figure recorded in 2022. Additionally, Rikken et al. (2023) noted that there were fewer than 500 DAOs in 2018. The origins of the first DAO have been a subject of debate. Some argue that Bitcoin effectively serves as the initial DAO (Buterin, 2020), while many others assert that The DAO, formed in 2016, holds this distinction (Faqir-Rhazoui et al., 2021; Santana and Albareda, 2022; Wang et al., 2019; Park et al., 2023).

The rapid development of DAOs reflects their increasing importance and diverse applications across various sectors. This explosive growth highlights how DAOs have evolved from their early definitions to become integral components of industries ranging from finance to supply chains to science. It further underscores the growing need to examine their operational mechanisms, particularly how incentives drive member engagement.

1.1. Literature review and motivation

DAO tokens extend beyond their transactional function and play a crucial role in member engagement. Several research studies have

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highlighted the multifaceted roles of tokens in governance, incentives, reputation, and economic benefits, which collectively strengthen the relationship between members and DAOs (Kaal, 2021; Santana and Albareda, 2022; Bellavitis et al., 2023).

1.1.1. DAO operation and control

DAO operation and control are facilitated primarily through the use of tokens, which represent a stake in the DAO's performance and are held by all stakeholders involved (Wankmüller et al., 2023). Tokens are central to DAO participant motivation, with economic incentives provided through token allocation (Wang et al., 2019). While most DAO tokens do not offer direct revenue-sharing, they symbolise a share of the organisation's potential earnings, linking token value to the DAO's financial success (Malinova and Park, 2023; Catalini and Gans, 2018). This notion is further supported by Chod and Lyandres (2021), Chod et al. (2022), who view DAO tokens as claims on the organisation's future revenue.

Furthermore, the market value of DAO tokens, or the total market capitalisation of the DAO, plays a crucial role in the organisation's valuation (Galea, 2022). As Pizzolato (2022) notes, the token value often mirrors the overall company value, enhancing the DAO's economic appeal. Beyond their financial function, tokens serve to foster member engagement by contributing to governance, reputation, and incentives (Kaal, 2021; Santana and Albareda, 2022; Bellavitis et al., 2023), thereby strengthening the connection between members and the DAO.

The operation of DAOs relies heavily on the contributions of their members, making it essential to understand the mechanisms by which these efforts are incentivised. The following section explores how DAOs reward members for their contributions, highlighting the strategies employed to motivate and sustain active participation.

1.1.2. Incentives for member efforts

This research draws on incentive theory and social exchange theory to clarify DAO operations. Incentive theory, as outlined by Lazear (2018), provides a framework for understanding how structured rewards drive effort and performance in traditional organisations, often using game-theoretic models to predict behaviours under specific incentives. However, directly applying traditional incentives to DAOs, a decentralised model, is challenging. Social exchange theory complements this by focusing on the exchange of benefits, where relationships are strengthened by maximising rewards and minimising costs (Lioukas and Reuer, 2015).

In DAOs, trust in token value mirrors monetary incentives in conventional settings (Toufaily, 2022; Tan and Saraniemi, 2023). Similar to financial rewards, tokens can serve as effective motivators, showing their role as valuable assets in digital environments. Combining these theories, this study seeks to explain token functionality within DAOs, where incentive theory provides foundational principles, and social exchange theory addresses the dynamics of trust in a digital, decentralised context.

Practically, token-based incentives in DAOs are complex. Typically, founders or investors hold a significant portion of the token supply, with only a limited percentage available for community rewards, released according to a predetermined schedule. This structured release of tokens ensures that only a restricted number of tokens are accessible for community rewards at any given time. Tokens are primarily utilised to mitigate free-riding in DAOs.

To further address free-riding, strategies such as performance underreporting, as explored by Bisetti et al. (2022), show potential for improving team performance in remote work settings, which this study explores in the DAO context. Talbot and Newman (2021) argue that game theory principles allow DAOs to align incentives across a supply chain without a single administrative structure, achieving coordination absent in traditional cooperatives. For example, unlike DAOs, cooperative members, such as Fonterra's farmers, are primarily incentivised

by increasing supply rather than engaging in broader organisational development.

Existing literature highlights the importance of member contributions in DAOs. Anson (2018) and Tsoukalas and Falk (2020) note that members who exert greater effort tend to receive more tokens, aligning token allocation with contribution. Similarly, Pizzolato (2022) and Galea (2022) suggest that tokens provide economic value, rewarding members in proportion to their contributions.

In the following section, we explore gaps in existing research on token allocation and its effectiveness in incentivising DAO members, outlining this study's contributions.

1.2. Research gap and contribution

While tokens represent a powerful incentive tool widely used in practice, we lack a theoretical framework describing how the tokens affect incentives in organisations. This study aims to address this gap by examining whether the association between efforts and tokens, which has not been explored in cooperatives or previous research on DAOs, can effectively motivate members to generate value for DAOs. Additionally, the paper investigates another characteristic commonly employed by DAOs in practice: the allocation percentage of DAO tokens for community rewards. This aspect, absent in cooperatives and previous research on DAOs, is considered in our analysis.

Our research highlights the role of members' active contribution as a key success factor for a DAO. We discovered that while a cooperative structure generally leads to lower equilibrium efforts as the number of members increases, large DAOs incentivise higher member efforts even with a small community reward fraction. Conversely, small organisations achieve the highest efforts through a cooperative structure or significant token allocation to community rewards. Additionally, tokens are one of the incentive mechanisms that can help induce effort and mitigate moral hazard problems in organisations.

The subsequent sections of this paper are organised as follows. Section 2 presents the game-theoretic model that elucidates the incentives within cooperatives and DAOs. Subsequently, in Section 3, we conduct a comparative analysis of the equilibrium efforts between cooperatives and DAOs. Section 4 illustrates special cases where the value function is linear in efforts. In Section 5, we explore an extension of the model that accounts for increased token value. In Section 6, we summarise our key findings, emphasising our work's significant contributions to theoretical understanding and practical applications. Furthermore, Section 6 outlines potential avenues for future research, identifying specific areas where further investigation could yield valuable insights and advance the field, building upon the foundations laid by our current study.

2. Model

In this section, we introduce the model and explore the first-best solution, which represents the ideal scenario for a member in a DAO. Additionally, we compare a DAO to a cooperative, focusing on the level of effort exerted by their respective members in facilitating the organisation's development.

Our model is grounded in standard game-theoretic assumptions commonly used in the theory of incentives. One fundamental assumption is that all members behave rationally, making decisions that maximise their utility. We also assume a deterministic relationship between effort and reward, where a specific level of effort reliably leads to a corresponding reward. Another critical assumption pertains to the sequence of decision-making within the DAO. Typically, DAOs distribute a predetermined quantity of tokens as community rewards within a defined timeframe, often on a monthly basis. Our model focuses on a specific time period during which a designated number of tokens is allocated for community rewards. Given the relatively short duration, all participants contribute to the DAO's development simultaneously, with limited opportunities to observe the actions of

others. Consequently, members must independently determine their level of effort during the specified period, resulting in a simultaneous game.

Each member decides how much effort e_i to put towards improving the DAO. Efforts are typically common knowledge. For example, everyone can verify how many supplier reviews a particular member left or how many products they listed on the DAO's platform. Member i receives ke_i token for their efforts, where $k > 0$. Exerting these efforts increase the number of tokens held by a member (Talbot and Newman, 2021), DAO's value increases by $v(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_i, \dots, e_n)$ as per Chod et al. (2022), for some organisations it can be the revenue, where n is the total number of members. For convenience, we denote this added value as $v(e)$ such that $\frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} > 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 v(e)}{\partial e_i^2} \leq 0$, where $e \equiv \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_i, \dots, e_n\}$, i.e., e is the set of efforts of all members and the Hessian matrix of $v(e)$ is negative semi-definite. For example, consider the case of ResearchHub DAO, where users contribute to the platform by writing and sharing high-quality articles, thereby exerting effort. These efforts result in the creation of added value for the ResearchHub platform as a whole. The efforts are costly, and the cost per Member i is denoted by $c_i(e_i)$, where $c_i(e_i)$ is such that $\frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i} > 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i^2} > 0$. In other words, each member may have a different effort cost function, reflecting potentially different abilities of different members.

After exerting e_i efforts, Member i will hold $\frac{ke_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n ke_j} = \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$ fraction of the total number of tokens distributed as rewards for participation in the DAO's initiatives. In reality, many DAOs distribute tokens to members based on their efforts. For example, DAOHaus rewards its members based on their efforts towards processing proposals of the DAO. They have separate parameters to decide on member efforts. Let us denote Member i 's share of tokens as $s_i(e) \equiv \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$.

The comparison in Fig. 1 illustrates the distinctions between DAOs and traditional member-owned organisations, such as cooperatives. Cooperative members cultivate multifaceted relationships with their organisation, engaging in both a transactional dynamic as users meet their needs and an investment relationship as proprietors of the cooperative (Billiet et al., 2021). As asserted by Verhees et al. (2015), member commitment functions as a glue, facilitating the cooperative in retaining its market share. Consequently, members with a high level of commitment may enjoy privileged access to specialised or niche products and services provided by the cooperative. Moreover, committed members are likely to experience expanded opportunities for increased influence and participation in the cooperative's decision-making processes.

Despite members contributing substantial effort towards organisational development within a traditional organisation, their share of the members' assets usually remains unaltered. However, in the context of a DAO, exerting additional effort by a member results in a proportional increase in their share of assets, represented by tokens. This distinction highlights a fundamental departure from the traditional model, emphasising the dynamic nature of asset distribution in DAOs.

Let us denote m , the fraction of tokens distributed as a reward for members' efforts, i.e., to motivate members to exert efforts, such that $0 < m \leq 1$.

We represent the share of tokens held by Member i as $s_i(e)$, and $s_i(e)$ is non-decreasing in e_i . This implies that as a member exerts more effort, the share of tokens they receive will either increase or remain unchanged in the worst case. As m is the fraction of tokens distributed to the members as a reward for their exerted efforts, members will each receive $ms_i(e)$, and $\sum_{j=1}^n s_j(e) = 1$. Therefore, $1 - ms_i(e)$ is the residual fraction that other members in the DAO receive; we will denote this residual fraction as $r_{-i}(e)$.

In this paper, we will leverage the concept of semi-elasticity to explain our key insights. The semi-elasticity of a function reflects the percentage change in the function value concerning an absolute change in the function argument. For example, the semi-elasticity of the value function for Member i shows by how much percent the added value

Fig. 1. Relationship between efforts and share of tokens of Member i .

will increase if Member i increases their efforts by one unit. It can be denoted as $\frac{\partial v(e)/\partial e_i}{v(e)}$ or $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i}$. Similarly, the semi-elasticity of the residual fraction function is the percentage change in the added value that all other members in the DAO receive if Member i increases their effort by one unit. This function can be represented as $\frac{\partial r_{-i}(e)/\partial e_i}{r_{-i}(e)}$ or $\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$, which is a non-positive value.

Subsequently, we will proceed to formalise the objective function. A hypothetical central decision-maker aims to maximise the added value in the first-best scenario, which serves as the ideal benchmark. The added value is defined as the difference between the total added value and the cost incurred by each member in the DAO. Therefore, the objective function can be expressed as,

$$\pi(e) = v(e) - \sum_{j=1}^n c_j(e_j) \quad (1)$$

2.1. DAO

In DAOs, each member maximises their objective function, and we will represent it in the decentralised scenario. In this case, a member will have a claim for a share of value (Chod et al. 2022). The objective function for Member i is,

$$\pi_i^D(e) = ms_i(e)v(e) - c_i(e_i) \quad (2)$$

In other words, each member will maximise their share of the added value less the cost of their efforts. Having established the decision variables and objective functions, we next identify a condition sufficient to ensure that each member exerts the first-best equilibrium effort.

Proposition 1. If $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = (>(<)) - \frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$, the equilibrium efforts will equal (less than) (greater than) the first-best efforts.

All proofs are provided in the appendix.

The left-hand side represents the semi-elasticity of the value function in the efforts of Member i , i.e., it shows the percentage change in the value function if Member i changes their effort. The right-hand side represents the semi-elasticity of the residual fraction of the added value that other members will receive. Proposition 1 states that the first-best outcome can be achieved if these two semi-elasticities are equal for all effort levels and all DAO members.

The intuition behind Proposition 1 is relatively simple. The first-best efforts are achieved if marginal efforts of Member i result in equal relative increases in the value for the entire DAO and the fraction of this value captured by Member i (or, more precisely, the relative decrease in the fraction captured by all other members).

Next, we are going to model the incentives for cooperatives.

2.2. Cooperative

According to the existing literature, cooperatives typically do not practice a policy that provides incentives based on the efforts exerted by their members towards the cooperative's development. Consequently, even if a member puts in significant effort to contribute to the cooperative's development, their value share will not increase. That means, for cooperatives, there is no m value; the fraction of tokens distributed as a reward for members' efforts is a unique feature for DAOs.

In this case, assuming a symmetric membership structure, irrespective of how many shares each member holds, everyone will get $1/n$ of the total added value, i.e., $s_i(e) = \frac{1}{n}$. Therefore, the objective function for Member i is,

$$\pi_i^C(e) = \frac{1}{n}v(e) - c_i(e_i) \tag{3}$$

Proposition 2. *In a cooperative, members will always exert efforts that are lower than the first-best efforts.*

Proposition 2 suggests that in the cooperative setting being modelled, there tend to be less-than-first-best effort levels from all members. This observation is consistent with the notion discussed by Holmstrom (1982) regarding moral hazard issues in teams. Within the context of specific cooperatives, individual efforts might contribute more to the overall organisation rather than yielding direct benefits to individual members. Consequently, there may be instances where individual members find it strategically advantageous to exert lower efforts.

Holmstrom (1982) had a similar focus and constructed a team production model in a labour-managed firm or a partnership. In that model, the author discussed an agent's share of the outcome, referred to as $s_i(v(e))$, and the share depends on the output. In this case, the share does not depend on the effort directly because efforts are unobservable. He argued that if the agent's effort falls short of the first-best level, it can be attributed to the free-rider problem, which results in inadequate effort supply. As per Proposition 1 in our model, the incentive system of the DAO will lead to higher efforts of the members. In our case, we assume the efforts are observable, so it is possible to have a sharing rule contingent on efforts. We have a different functional form for DAOs, $s_i(e) \cdot v(e)$ and under this function, the share of tokens should not depend on the organisation's value but on efforts only. Therefore, our model can achieve the first-best effort under the conditions, $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = -\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$ and $m = 1$.

The subsequent section investigates several scenarios for cooperative and DAO equilibrium efforts.

3. Comparison of equilibrium efforts of cooperatives and DAOs

In this section, we aim to compare the efforts between cooperatives and DAOs. When establishing an organisation, members seek to optimise their value, which is done through the maximisation of their efforts. Hence, the comparison of efforts is crucial in determining the suitable organisational form between cooperatives and DAOs.

Proposition 3 compares cooperatives' and DAOs' efforts for the case efforts. When it holds for any efforts, it should hold for equilibrium efforts. This means cooperative equilibrium efforts will equal the DAO equilibrium efforts.

Proposition 3. *If $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = (<)(>)\frac{nm \sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - e_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - nme_i)}$, the equilibrium cooperative efforts will be equal to (greater than) (less than) the equilibrium DAO efforts.*

In the $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = \frac{nm \sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - e_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - nme_i)}$ equation, for any effort, the value function only depends on the efforts. Therefore, the left-hand side is independent of m , but the right-hand side depends on m . Suppose the equation holds, and thus, the equilibrium efforts are the same for cooperatives and DAOs. If the fraction of tokens distributed as a reward

for members' efforts, denoted as m , increases, equilibrium efforts for cooperatives will be less than those for DAOs.

For DAOs, the fraction of tokens held by a member will be equivalent to the share of the company owned by the member. When all the tokens are distributed to the members as an incentive for the DAO development, DAO founders will not hold a fraction of the token supply for them. In other words, the fraction of the value captured by Member i will equal the share of tokens held by that member, i.e., $ms_i(e) = \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$, where $m = 1$.

In a DAO, $ms_i(e) = \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$. Therefore, the objective function for Member i is,

$$\pi_i^D(e) = \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot v(e) - c_i(e_i) \tag{4}$$

Corollary 1 introduces the condition sufficient to achieve the first-best efforts for DAOs under a hypothetical scenario when $m = 1$.

Corollary 1. *If $m = 1$ and $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$, the DAO equilibrium efforts will equal the first-best efforts.*

This corollary serves as an illustrative example, showcasing the potential for a DAO to achieve the first-best efforts. However, it is possible if and only if all tokens of the DAO are distributed as community rewards. In Corollary 1, we established the necessary conditions for a DAO to achieve the first-best efforts.

In the following section, we will provide special cases to illustrate the conditions outlined in the above propositions and when they hold.

4. Special case: Value function linear in efforts

In this section, we will examine a particular functional form to check if it holds. In this scenario, we consider that, $v(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j$. When the effects of efforts are independent of one another, additive efforts are the best way to capture the efforts (Lee and Li, 2018). It is a prevalent scenario that efforts are additive, and we will have an idea of what the condition will look like for additive efforts. DAOs are usually organisations with a large number of members, and there is no chance of interaction between the efforts of members, which means the effect of the efforts of one member is independent of the other.

4.1. Equilibrium efforts of DAOs

Within this segment, we explore the feasibility of DAOs achieving first-best efforts under a linear value function and examine the necessary conditions for such achievement. Additionally, we investigate some properties of equilibrium efforts within DAOs.

Proposition 4. *If $m = 1$ and efforts are additive, the DAO equilibrium efforts will equal the first-best efforts.*

In the above proposition, we assumed that Member i captures the fraction of value directly proportional to the fraction of tokens they receive for their efforts. This assumption holds if all tokens are distributed to DAO members for their efforts.

Proposition 5. *When $m < 1$, and efforts are additive, the DAO equilibrium efforts will be less than the first-best efforts.*

Intuitively, when m decreases, the member's share of the organisation diminishes, leading to a decrease in equilibrium efforts. In this section, we verified a special case of Proposition 1, examining whether the inequality, $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} > -\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$, ever holds. This observation implies that a DAO will never achieve the first-best efforts when some tokens are not distributed as a reward for members' efforts. In this context, we observe that the use of additive efforts ensures its validity.

In Proposition 6, we will examine how changing the fraction of tokens distributed as a reward for members' efforts affects equilibrium efforts.

Proposition 6. *The equilibrium efforts will increase (decrease) as m increases (decreases).*

Intuitively, equilibrium efforts are expected to increase (decrease) as m increases (decreases). Upon comparing DAO equilibrium efforts with first-best efforts, we observe a clear dependency of DAO equilibrium efforts on m , while first-best efforts do not vary with m . This confirms **Proposition 5**: for any m value less than 1, DAO equilibrium efforts will be less than first-best efforts. In the case of $m = 1$, DAO equilibrium efforts will equal first-best efforts.

In practice, as a DAO distributes fewer tokens to the community, the community members have less incentive to exert effort. This emphasises the critical link between token distribution and the motivation levels of community members within the DAO ecosystem, highlighting the need for thoughtful token allocation to maximise participant engagement and effort contribution.

Next, we will explore the correlation between the number of members in cooperatives and DAOs and the proportion of tokens allocated to community rewards.

4.2. Comparison of DAOs to cooperatives

When choosing the right organisational form, the consideration of the number of members is crucial. In the case of a DAO, the proportion of tokens allocated to community rewards must be considered simultaneously with the number of participating members for optimal performance compared to a cooperative.

Proposition 7 examines the relationship between the number of members in the organisation (n) and the fraction of tokens dedicated to community rewards (m) to determine which scenario leads to higher equilibrium efforts.

Proposition 7. *If $m > (<)(=)1/n$, then the DAO equilibrium efforts will be greater than (less than) (equal to) the cooperative equilibrium efforts.*

Fig. 2 illustrates the relationship between the organisational structure and the level of equilibrium efforts exhibited by members of DAO and cooperatives. This relationship depends upon the number of members in the organisation (n) and the fraction of tokens dedicated to community rewards (m).

In particular, **Fig. 2** shows that large DAOs will achieve higher efforts than cooperatives of the same size even if the fraction of tokens dedicated to the community rewards is relatively low. Conversely, if the community reward fraction is relatively large, even smaller DAOs will achieve higher efforts.

Interestingly, as presented in **Proposition 7**, at $m = 1$, the DAO allows for achieving the first-best efforts. At that point, even the smallest possible DAO with just one member will incentivise higher equilibrium efforts than a cooperative of the same size. Nevertheless, the allocation of all tokens exclusively for community rewards is not a prevalent practice in real-world scenarios. This is due to the fact that tokens often serve multiple purposes, including but not limited to rewarding early investors, establishing reserves, facilitating exchange liquidity provision, and fulfilling other functions, as previously discussed in the introduction section.

The underlying rationale behind the observed relationship between equilibrium efforts in DAOs and cooperatives is as follows. As a cooperative gets larger, i.e., attracts more members, its members receive a lower fraction of the added value, which refers to the profits they receive. It was discussed in the introduction that a cooperative does not incentivise its members' efforts through tokens, which is likely to affect the efforts that members put in order to develop the cooperative. Consequently, cooperative members tend to exhibit significantly lower levels of equilibrium efforts.

In contrast, this phenomenon is not observed in DAOs due to the compensatory mechanism provided by tokens received as rewards. Even when the fraction of value allocated to individual members is

Fig. 2. Equilibrium efforts for DAOs and cooperatives.

reduced, the tokens received act as a form of compensation. Simultaneously, the effectiveness of this compensation diminishes when the allocation of tokens to community members is small.

These findings have practical implications for decision-makers in selecting the optimal organisational structure based on the organisation's size and the fraction of tokens dedicated to community rewards.

5. Extension: Enhanced value of tokens

The implementation of smart contract systems that facilitate human and machine coordination and decision-making can be instrumental (DuPont, 2019). By utilising smart contracts, DAOs can ensure compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks (Sims, 2019), ensuring that all members are treated in accordance with the terms specified in the contract. While DAOs perform similar functions to traditional member-owned organisations, there are notable differences in task coordination, characterised by increased transparency and a digital nature (Buterin, 2020; Hsieh et al., 2018), particularly concerning operations and agreements. Some DAOs could have their smart contracts structured in such a way that the tokens hold a value greater than their economic value. In this situation, members with more tokens have more power than those with fewer tokens (Kaal, 2021; Santana and Albareda, 2022; Bellavitis et al., 2023). We extend our model to illustrate a scenario in which tokens hold greater value than their economic value, i.e., introduce the new value share function. **Proposition 8** depicts the non-linear effect of the share of tokens.

In this extension, we posit that possessing more tokens can significantly enhance a member's role in governance, thereby increasing their non-linear value. Specifically, we illustrate that the value to the member will increase exponentially.

Accordingly, the share of the value received by Member i is $S_i = \frac{e_i^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2}$, where S_i is the fraction of the token supply as community rewards. The member value increases at a much higher rate as they exert more effort and consequently receive more tokens. **Proposition 8** depicts the non-linear effect of the share of tokens.

Proposition 8. If $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = (<)(>)$ $\frac{2nme_i(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2 - e_i^2)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2)(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2 - nme_i^2)}$, the equilibrium cooperative efforts will be equal to (greater than) (less than) the equilibrium DAO efforts.

The result of Proposition 8 remains structurally similar to that of Proposition 3, indicating that the efforts of DAO members can be higher, lower, or equal to those of cooperative members. However, the threshold differs in this scenario because DAO members have more incentives to exert higher efforts.

6. Conclusion

In this section, we provide a summary of our findings and managerial implications and outline avenues for future research.

6.1. Theoretical implications

Our game-theoretic model explores incentives within cooperatives and DAOs, revealing both similarities and significant differences between these organisational structures. Traditional cooperatives face challenges with free-rider behaviour, where unlinked rewards to individual efforts lead to suboptimal member contributions (Ben-Ner and Ellman, 2013; Van Dijk et al., 2019). Holmstrom's (1982) team production model notes that cooperatives often fail to align individual rewards with individual contributions, leading to reduced effort levels. By contrast, DAOs have a mechanism that directly addresses this issue by tying rewards to observable individual efforts. Our findings show that DAOs achieve higher levels of member effort and engagement through an effort-based reward system, effectively mitigating free-rider problems and increasing member satisfaction.

Our analysis demonstrates that DAOs can reach first-best effort levels when token allocations reflect each member's marginal contributions to the organisation's value. In situations where all tokens are distributed solely as rewards, members of a DAO are incentivised to exert maximum effort, achieving optimal outcomes. This approach starkly contrasts with cooperative models, where effort levels generally fall below the optimum due to collective distribution structures. When cooperative and DAO models are compared, DAOs exhibit the potential to drive member contributions significantly higher, especially when tokens are allocated based on individual efforts, directly linking personal effort to personal reward.

Furthermore, our study highlights how DAOs might maintain equivalent or even superior effort levels compared to cooperatives under specific conditions. For instance, in scenarios with additive effort functions or where a limited token supply is allocated to community rewards, DAOs can maintain comparable efforts. However, as membership increases, cooperatives experience a decline in equilibrium efforts, while larger DAOs continue to incentivise higher member engagement even with a modest community reward allocation. These theoretical insights offer a foundation for understanding how DAOs leverage token-based incentives to sustain higher member efforts, especially in larger organisations.

6.2. Managerial implications

This study offers practical guidance for founders, managers, and investors seeking to optimise member contributions within DAOs and cooperatives. By directly tying individual rewards to contributions, DAOs address the free-rider problem that often challenges cooperatives. In traditional cooperatives, member efforts are often unlinked from rewards, leading to dissatisfaction and reduced effort. In contrast, DAOs allocate tokens based on observable efforts, fostering a system of fair compensation that enhances motivation and productivity.

Organisational size plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of these models. For large organisations, DAOs generally outperform cooperatives in sustaining high effort levels, even with a moderate allocation of

tokens. For example, in a large DAO like ResearchHub, the token-based incentive structure proves effective by incentivising many members who do not directly interact. These tokens motivate members, especially in settings where anonymous members lack a personal connection to the community. By distributing tokens reflecting individual contributions, ResearchHub maintains high engagement within its vast, decentralised network.

For smaller organisations, a cooperative model may be more appropriate, particularly if members are closely connected and directly invested in the organisation's collective value. For instance, in a smaller setting like UC Crypto Soc, where each member's contributions are shared among fewer people, the cooperative structure aligns better with member interests. Here, members may be more motivated by owning a share of the organisation's value than by relying on token distribution. However, if UC Crypto Soc were to operate as a DAO, it would need to allocate more tokens for rewards to maintain engagement. This approach could mitigate free-rider issues but may limit resources for activities like marketing and community development.

These insights underscore the importance of tailoring organisational models to fit both the size and nature of the community. Large DAOs can optimise efforts by calibrating reward systems to ensure tokens are valuable and accessible. Smaller cooperatives might benefit from incorporating performance-based rewards inspired by DAOs, enhancing motivation and aligning member goals with organisational objectives.

Ultimately, the decision to form a DAO or a cooperative should depend on organisational size, member engagement dynamics, and the desired level of incentivisation. For large decentralised entities like ResearchHub, a DAO model is preferable due to the scalability of its incentives. Smaller organisations, like UC Crypto Soc, might thrive as cooperatives, where members are motivated by ownership shares rather than token-based rewards.

6.3. Future research

This study is one of the first to analyse incentives in DAOs based on the efforts of members for the development of the organisation and may provide a fertile ground for future research. While this study establishes a sufficient condition for achieving the first-best effort, future research could be directed towards defining the set of necessary and sufficient conditions. In particular, we have considered a general function for the value function and showed that DAOs could achieve the first-best efforts if the value function is linear and additive in efforts. However, future research can be achieved with other functional forms of the value function.

As a general rule, tokens of a DAO can be transferred or sold among the members of the DAO or to an external party. However, it is possible to set up a DAO with non-transferable tokens. Future research can shed light on the effect of token transferability on incentives to help DAOs establish a better governance structure. Additionally, exploring the impact of uncertainty on equilibrium outcomes and how deviations from rational behaviour, including risk aversion or risk-seeking tendencies, influence decision-making in DAOs, could be promising.

The role of token functionality in incentivising DAO members also requires more research. Tokens may give voting rights to their holders, potentially increasing the value of tokens and providing even higher incentives for token holders. For example, some DAOs design incentives for participants who consume energy more efficiently upon proof (Kim and Chung, 2018; Voshmgir, 2020). As we can see, DAOs possess a powerful arsenal of decisions on token allocation, token functionality, and governance structure to incentivise their members. Given the complex nature of interactions between DAO members, the consequences of these decisions are not always intuitive. In this light, the further role of the research community is to explore different combinations of key DAO decisions to find perfect recipes for DAOs of various sizes, compositions, and objectives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mevni Manarangi Piyarisi: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Timofey Shalpegin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Appendix. Proof

Proof of Proposition 1. Let us rewrite $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = -\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$ as $\frac{\partial v(e)/\partial e_i}{v(e)} = \frac{\partial ms_i(e)/\partial e_i}{1-ms_i(e)}$. We can find the equilibrium efforts for the decentralised case from the set of derivatives for Member i 's objective function: $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial ms_i(e)}{\partial e_i} \cdot v(e) + ms_i(e) \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$. Similarly, for the first-best case, the optimal effort can be found from $\frac{\partial \pi(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$. By substituting $\frac{\partial ms_i(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial v(e)/\partial e_i}{v(e)} \cdot (1 - ms_i(e))$ in $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i}$, we obtain $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \pi(e)}{\partial e_i}$, which will result in the same equilibrium efforts for the DAO and first-best cases.

Let e^{D^*} be such that $\frac{\partial ms_i(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} \cdot v(e^{D^*}) + ms_i(e^{D^*}) \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$ and let e^* be such that $\frac{\partial v(e^*)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^*)}{\partial e_i}$, i.e., e^{D^*} is the Nash equilibrium effort in the decentralised scenario and e^* is the first-best optimal effort.

First, $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} > -\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$ is equivalent to $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial ms_i(e)/\partial e_i}{1-ms_i(e)}$, from which it follows that $\frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial ms_i(e)}{\partial e_i} \cdot v(e) + ms_i(e) \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i}$. Therefore, $\frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial ms_i(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} \cdot v(e^{D^*}) + ms_i(e^{D^*}) \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$. Note that $\frac{\partial ms_i(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} \cdot v(e^{D^*}) + ms_i(e^{D^*}) \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$, which means $\frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$.

Noting that $\frac{\partial v(e^*)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^*)}{\partial e_i}$ and the fact that $\frac{\partial^2 v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i^2} \leq 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i^2} > 0$ we obtain $e^* > e^{D^*}$, which means the first-best efforts are greater than the equilibrium efforts in the decentralised scenario.

Proof for the other scenario is analogous. \square

Proof of Proposition 2. To find the equilibrium efforts, we take the partial derivative with respect to e_i , which is, $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$.

Let e^{C^*} be such that $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} = 0$ and let e^* be such that $\frac{\partial v(e^*)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^*)}{\partial e_i}$, i.e., e^{C^*} is the Nash equilibrium effort in the decentralised scenario and e^* is the first-best optimal effort.

As $n > 1$, we obtain $\frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} > \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i}$. Noting that $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i}$, we obtain $\frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i}$.

Noting that $\frac{\partial v(e^*)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^*)}{\partial e_i}$ and the fact that $\frac{\partial^2 v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i^2} \leq 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i^2} > 0$, we obtain $e^* > e^{C^*}$, which means the equilibrium efforts in a cooperative will be lower than the first-best efforts. \square

Proof of Proposition 3. In Proposition 3, we first present the proof for the equality case. Let us rewrite $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = \frac{nm \sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - e_i)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - nme_i)}$ as

$\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \left(\frac{m \cdot e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot v(e) \right)}{\partial e_i}$. We can find the equilibrium efforts for the DAO case, $\pi_i^D(e) = \frac{m \cdot e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot v(e) - c_i(e_i)$ from the set of derivatives for its objective function: $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = m \left[\frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot v(e) \right] - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$.

Similarly, for the cooperative case, $\pi_i^C(e) = \frac{1}{n} \cdot v(e) - c_i(e_i)$, the optimal effort can be found from $\frac{\partial \pi_i^C(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$. By substituting $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial e_i} \left(\frac{m \cdot e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot v(e) \right)$ in $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i}$, we obtain $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \pi_i^C(e)}{\partial e_i}$, which will result in the same equilibrium efforts for the DAO and cooperative cases.

Now, let us provide proof of inequality.

Let e^{D^*} be such that $m \left[\frac{e_i^{D^*}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i^{D^*}}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot v(e^{D^*}) \right] = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$ and let e^{C^*} be such that $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i}$, i.e., e^{C^*} is the Nash equilibrium efforts in the cooperative structure and e^{D^*} is the DAO Nash equilibrium efforts.

First, $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} > \frac{nm \sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - e_i)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - nme_i)}$ is equivalent to $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial \left(\frac{m \cdot e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot v(e) \right)}{\partial e_i}$, from which it follows that $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} > m \left[\frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot v(e) \right]$. Therefore, $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} > m \left[\frac{e_i^{D^*}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i^{D^*}}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot v(e^{D^*}) \right]$. Note that $m \left[\frac{e_i^{D^*}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i^{D^*}}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot v(e^{D^*}) \right] = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$, which means $\frac{\partial v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i} > \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$.

Noting that $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e^{C^*})}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i}$, and the fact that $\frac{\partial^2 v(e^{D^*})}{\partial e_i^2} \leq 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 c_i(e_i^{C^*})}{\partial e_i^2} > 0$, we obtain $e^{C^*} > e^{D^*}$, which means the cooperative equilibrium efforts are greater than the DAO equilibrium efforts.

Proof for the other scenario is analogous. \square

Proof of Corollary 1. To find the DAO equilibrium efforts, we take the partial derivative of $\pi_i^D(e)$ with respect to e_i is

$$\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \sum_{j=1}^n e_j}{\partial e_i} \cdot v(e) + \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$$

Simplifying we obtain

$$\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (e_j - e_i)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot v(e) + \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$$

For the first-best case, the optimal effort can be determined by the partial derivative with respect to e_i , and this can be found from $\frac{\partial \pi(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$.

By substituting $\frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} = \frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i}$ in $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i}$, we obtain $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \pi(e)}{\partial e_i}$, which will result in the same equilibrium efforts for the DAOs and first-best cases. \square

Proof of Proposition 4. If $v(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j$ and $s_i(e) = \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$, $m = 1$ where $a > 0$, the objective function is as follows:

$$\pi(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j - \sum_{j=1}^n c_j(e_j)$$

The objective function for Member i is,

$$\pi_i^a(e) = \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} + a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j - c_i(e_i)$$

The partial derivative with respect to e_i is,

$$\frac{\partial \pi_i^a(e)}{\partial e_i} = a - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_i^a(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)^2} \cdot a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j + \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} \cdot a - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$$

We obtain $\frac{\partial \pi_i^a(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \pi(e)}{\partial e_i}$, which will result in the same equilibrium efforts for the DAO and first-best cases. \square

Proof of Proposition 5. If $v(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j$ and $s_i(e) = \frac{m \cdot e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$ where $a > 0$,

let us rewrite $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial v(e)/\partial e_i}{v(e)}$, when $v(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j$, $\frac{\partial v(e)/\partial e_i}{v(e)} = \frac{\partial (a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j)/\partial e_i}{a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j} = \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$. And we will rewrite, $-\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$ as $\frac{\partial ms_i(e)/\partial e_i}{1-ms_i(e)}$. By substituting $s_i(e) = \frac{m \cdot e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$, we receive $\frac{\partial (m \sum_{j=1}^n e_j)/\partial e_i}{1-m \sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$. By simplifying, we obtain $\frac{m(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - m \cdot e_i)(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)}$.

Therefore, $m \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} < \frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$ and $\frac{1}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} > \frac{m(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - m \cdot e_i)(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j)}$ which means $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} > -\frac{\partial \ln(r_{-i}(e))}{\partial e_i}$, and the equilibrium efforts will always be less than the first-best efforts. \square

Proof of Proposition 6. If $v(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j$ and $s_i(e) = \frac{me_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$, where $a > 0$, the objective function is as follows:

$$\pi(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j - \sum_{j=1}^n c_j(e_j)$$

The objective function for Member i is,

$$\pi_i^D(e) = \frac{me_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} - a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j - c_i(e_i)$$

The partial derivative with respect to e_i is,

$$\frac{\partial \pi(e)}{\partial e_i} = a - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$$

$$\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = am - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$$

From the above, it follows that equilibrium efforts for DAOs will increase (decrease) as m increases (decreases). Furthermore, for any $m < 1$, the DAO equilibrium efforts will always be less than the first-best efforts. □

Proof of Proposition 7. If $v(e) = a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j$ and $ms_i(e) = \frac{me_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j}$, where $a > 0$, then the DAO objective function is as follows:

$$\pi_i^D(e) = m \cdot \frac{e_i}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j} - a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j - c_i(e_i) = me_i a - c_i(e_i)$$

The cooperative function stays as follows:

$$\pi_i^C(e) = \frac{1}{n} a \sum_{j=1}^n e_j - c_i(e_i)$$

To find the equilibrium efforts, we take the partial derivative of a cooperative function with respect to e_i , which is $\frac{\partial \pi_i^C(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{1}{n} a - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$ and let $e_i^{C^*}$ such that $\frac{1}{n} a = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$. The partial derivative of a DAO function with respect to e_i is $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = ma - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$ let $e_i^{D^*}$ be such that $ma = \frac{\partial c_i(e_i^{D^*})}{\partial e_i}$, i.e., e^{C^*} is the Nash equilibrium efforts in the cooperative structure and e^{D^*} is the DAO Nash equilibrium efforts.

When $m > (<)(=)\frac{1}{n}$, we obtain $e^{D^*} > (<)(=)e^{C^*}$ which means the DAO equilibrium efforts will be greater than (less than) (equal to) the cooperative equilibrium efforts. □

Proof of Proposition 8. Let us rewrite $\frac{\partial \ln(v(e))}{\partial e_i} = \frac{2nme_i(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2 - e_i^2)}{(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2)(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2 - nme_i^2)}$

as $\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \left(m \cdot \frac{e_i^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2} \cdot v(e) \right)}{\partial e_i}$. We can find the equilibrium efforts for the

DAO case, $\pi_i^D(e) = m \cdot \frac{e_i^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2} \cdot v(e) - c_i(e_i)$, from the set of derivatives

for its objective function: $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = m \left[\frac{e_i^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} + \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j - e_i}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^n e_j \right)^2} \cdot v(e) \right] -$

$\frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$. Similarly, for the cooperative case, $\pi_i^C(e) = \frac{1}{n} v(e) - c_i(e_i)$, the

optimal effort can be found from $\frac{\partial \pi_i^C(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} - \frac{\partial c_i(e_i)}{\partial e_i}$. By substituting

$\frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{\partial v(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \left(m \cdot \frac{e_i^2}{\sum_{j=1}^n e_j^2} \cdot v(e) \right)}{\partial e_i}$ in $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i}$, we obtain $\frac{\partial \pi_i^D(e)}{\partial e_i} = \frac{\partial \pi_i^C(e)}{\partial e_i}$, which will result in the same equilibrium efforts for the DAO and cooperative cases. □

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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